

ANALYSIS OF THE ANTHROPONYMS USED IN ALPOMISH EPIC

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Annotation: The article describes the lexical-semantic, nominative-motivational, and stylistic features of Alpomish anthroponyms representing the nickname in the "Alpomish" epic.

Keywords: anthroponym, onomastics, "speaking name", biblionym, linguocultural, lexical base, poetonym.

INTRODUCTION

"Alpomish" is a rare artistic, encyclopedic and scientific value of world importance, because the work reflects not only the virtues of one people, but also the thoughts and imagination of the whole humanity, the feeling of loyalty to the Motherland, pure human love, humanitarianism and internationalism, a prosperous life and the ideas of freedom were put forward. Today, this epic is called "The Happy Childhood of Humanity". It can be said that it is one of the classic examples of the world epic like "Iliad" [1].

"Alpomish" reflects all the richness and color of the Uzbek folk language in terms of language. The epic also shows how juicy, how concise, and how perfect and rich the Uzbek folk language is for expressing one's life. The epic "Alpomish" is a masterpiece that showcases the richness, charm, and inner potential of the national language.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

As the famous linguist N. Mahmudov rightly stated, in the "Alpomish" saga, the ancient and always popular language of the Uzbek people shines with its full potential.

It can be said without any exaggeration that the epic "Alpomish" is an inexhaustible mirror of the Uzbek folk language, a reflection of the living history of the living folk language and folk wisdom[2,27].

In the "Alpomish" saga, all types of nouns characteristic of the Uzbek people and language: anthroponyms (names of people, nicknames), toponyms (names of places), hydronyms (names of lakes), oronyms (names of mountains, gorges, caves), zoonyms (animal names), ethnonyms (names of clan, tribe, nation) are actively used. As a product of the Uzbek people's way of life, customs, and traditions, these famous names provide rich information about the history, language, culture, and ethnography of our people.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the "Alpomish" epic, anthroponyms appear in different forms and variants: Hakimbek, Barchin, Boybori, Boysari, Karajan, Galdirgoch, Qultoy, Ko'kaldosh, Kokaman, Kokkasha, Boykasha, Toykasha, Koshkuloq, Yartiboy, Alpinbiy, Dovonbiy, Suhayil, Tovka, Yodgor. , Bodom, Ultontoz, Kayqubad, Toychakhan, Suqsuroy. All these anthroponyms have their own lexical-semantic and stylistic features.

The real name of Alpomish is Hakimbek, the protagonist of the work. The name Hakimbek was created by adding the word bek, which is used in nouns, to the Arabic word hakim, which means "knowledgeable, intelligent, wise, wise" [3,568-569]. Bek word 1) ruler, governor, chief; 2) solid, protected; means strong powerful [4,497].

So, the name Hakimbek has the anthroponymic meaning of "smart, wise, knowledgeable, strong, powerful ruler, chief".

In the epic, Shahimardan Piri Boybori's son was named Hakimbek, he dreamed and wanted this. This opinion is confirmed by the following prayers of Shahimardan Piri during the naming ceremony of Hakimbek: "... May no one be equal to Hakimbek, amen Allahu Akbar" [5,6].

This way of carrying out the ceremony of naming a child is very important in determining Hakimbek's life destiny. Naming a child according to the rules accepted in our values is not easily done in our nation. A feast is held in the country for the thanksgiving of the child. He is named after a long-lived, rich, wise, knowledgeable old man. The given name should be as meaningful as possible. It is known that Fazil Yoldosh insists that the event of naming his son Hakimbek took place based on our values. Since the person who gave the name was the elder of Shahimardan, the footprint of his paw protected Hakimbek from various disasters and tragedies. At the same time, he connected his fate with the fate of Barchinoy [6,39].

Later, Hakimbek was named Alpomish for his bravery and bravery. Alpomish's anthroponym is based on the pure Turkic word alp, which means "brave, warrior".

In the saga, Hakimbek was given this name as follows: "Hakimbek was seven years old. Alpinbi had a brilliant bow from his grandfather, which was made up of fourteen botomons. That's when the seven-year-old boy Hakimbek shul holds a fourteen-foot bow in his hand and pulls it. The arrow of the bow goes like lightning, passes through the great peaks of Mount Askar, and its sound goes to the world..."

Then all the people came together and said: "Nearly ninety alpins have passed away, the leader of the alpins was Rustami Doston, let this Alpomish alpin be the last." In the end, Alpomishbek became an alpine, one of the ninety-alpine, who passed to the date, raised an alpine horse, and at the age of seven, Alpomish was given a horse. Alpomish was named Alp because he shot a bow at the age of seven [5,9].

The emergence of many names in the Uzbek language is inextricably linked with national, religious, customs, images, traditions, beliefs and imaginations. It was believed that the child's health and future happiness depend on the name given to him. It was believed that the name given to a baby has a great influence on its fate and life, the name embodies the psyche and destiny of a person, and a person is like his name. Therefore, most names represent noble desires. This is more evident in the names of literary figures. The name of most of the symbols is proportional to the idea, the theme being depicted, more precisely, the names of the symbols in the work also carry artistic content with their essence. For example, "Alpomish" is called Alpomish because the main character of the epic is a fighter, strong, powerful and fearless.

When you read the epic "Alpomish", you will witness that the people created Alpomish as a wrestler who "doesn't pass if he is set on fire, and cannot be shot by a rifleman". In onomastics there is a term called "speaking names". Speaking names refer to their meaning with the form of names. He gives vivid images of the person, object, and event that he is shooting. Alpomish anthroponym is one of such names. The anthroponym of Alpomish and the image of Alpomish show the harmony of form and content, the balance of language and life. In accordance with its name, Alpomish is embodied as a wrestler in the epic. From the beginning to the end of the saga, it shows its worth. This is clearly seen in his trip to the Kalmyk region, in fulfilling Barchin's conditions. That is probably why this heroic epic was called "Alpomish", that is, the anthroponym of Alpomish was raised to the level of the name of the work-biblionym, and another type of famous horse was made from one type of horse.

CONCLUSION

The anthroponym of Alpomish is accepted in the Uzbek language and culture as a standard of honor and nobility, alpineness, valor, and strength. Therefore, later this anthroponym is used in artistic texts to create associations of "the pride of the Uzbek people, the brave defender of their country". In this case, Alpomish poetonym forms an onomastic metaphor and serves for the expressiveness of artistic content [7,17]. This is observed in several poems of Muhammad Yusuf

alone: Alpomishlar tug'ilajak, Baxting boshga gultoj endi, O'zbekmomo (M. Yusuf. O'zbekmomo).

Or

Erk degani o'zi kelib eshik qoqmas,
Jon chekmasang osmonlardan omad yog'mas.
Qatoringda botirlaring bo'lsin og'mas,
Gurkirasin Alpomishlar o'tgan tuproq,
Inshoolloh! [8,10].

References:

1. Joraev M. The saga of epics // Tashkent Evening, 1999, October 20, No. 122.
2. Mahmudov N. Til.-Tashkent: Writer, 1998.
3. Абдурахманова, С. Е. (2016). Современные транспортные магистрали Великого шелкового пути в Евразии. Молодой ученый, (3), 723-726.
4. Собиржонова, М. В., Атаханова, Ю. Ю., & Назарова, М. Т. (2018). СЕСТРИНСКОЕ ДЕЛО В ПЕДИАТРИИ. Мировая наука, (12 (21)), 396-399.
5. Собиржонова, М. В., Атаханова, Ю. Ю., & Холматова, Ё. Н. (2019). МИОПИЯ-ПРОБЛЕМА XXI ВЕКА. Мировая наука, (11 (32)), 298-301.
6. Собиржонова, М. В., Жураева, М. Г., & Назарова, М. Т. (2019). МЕДИЦИНСКОЕ НАБЛЮДЕНИЕ ДЕТЕЙ ПЕРВОГО ГОДА ЖИЗНИ. Теория и практика современной науки, (1), 452-455.
7. Холматова, Ё., Собиржонова, М., & Жураева, М. (2020). ДОСТИГНУТЫЕ УСПЕХИ В ИММУНОПРОФИЛАКТИКЕ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН. Мировая наука, (1 (34)), 554-556.
8. Sadikov, E. (2022). TIL O 'QITISHDA PRAGMATIKA MASALALARI: TA'RIFLAR, TANQIDLAR, Tahlillar va talqinlar. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz), 24(24).
9. Sadikov, E. (2022). How pragmatic skills can help improve students' conversational skills. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz), 24(24).
10. Tursunovich, S. E. (2022). Classification of compliments as speech acts and their basic characteristics in Uzbek and English languages. Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching, 4, 77-79.
11. Yuldasheva, D. (2022). METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING STUDENTS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH (ON THE EXAMPLE OF TOURISM DIRECTIONS). Science and innovation, 1(B7), 1498-1501.

12. Ашурбаева, Р. К. (2020). Концепция интеграции и ее применение в образовании SOI: 1.1/TAS DOI: 10.15863/TAS. Теоретические и прикладные науки, 2.
13. Ashurbaeva, R. K. (2021). Ways of effective Implementation of Integration. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 10.
14. Xaitov, L. A. (2021, December). THE ISSUE OF SUSTENANCE AND PROFESSION IN HAKIM TERMIZI'S WORK "BAYANUL KASB"("DESCRIPTION OF THE PROFESSION"). In International Scientific and Current Research Conferences (pp. 67-69).

